

ELIXIR Commissioned Service [2024-SCIENCE-BFSP, WP4 - HARVEST: Handling and alignment of plant research FAIRification – value through the use of ELIXIR data Standards and Tools]

D 4.1: Generate exemplary datasets as reference RO-Crates

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

This work package aimed to analyse the structure, metadata requirements and the current level of standardisation of existing datasets and focus on their FAIRification to provide them as FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) in the form of RO-Crates. Therefore different datasets, which were generously shared by the partners from the DROPS and AGENT project as well other already published datasets from several repositories were considered. Additionally, the European Variation Archive investigated RO-Crate packaging and implemented a new endpoint to describe its studies, enabling dynamic JSON-LD generation and ensuring interoperability with other life science data infrastructures.

Due to the high complexity of the data from the AGENT and DROPS datasets, a manual step-by-step transformation and the writing of contextual entities for the RO-Crate metadata file turned out to be extremely time-consuming. Therefore we decided to use the existing ARC-RO-Crate profile and the provided tools namely the ARCCitect as it facilitates the metadata annotation and provides an embedded RO-Crate export. As the AGENT datasets is currently part of a comprehensive research publication that is under review the refurbished datasets as FDO is still private due to editorial restrictions and will be released later. Work on the DROPS dataset was postponed due to delayed personnel hiring.

Beside these project related datasets we also analysed and restructured an historical phenotyping datasets of wheat that we extracted from a previous publication. It is stored as ARC in the PLANTdataHUB, which provides built-in functionality using the mentioned ARC-RO-Crate profile to export RO-Crate JSON.

Document info

Responsible Participant	Daniel Arend
Dissemination level	PU

Author List

Node	Institution	Name, surname	ORCID
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DE - Germany	Germany - Leibniz-Institut für Pflanzengenetik und Kulturpflanzenforschung (IPK), Stadt Seeland	Daniel Arend	0000-0002-2455-5938
DE - Germany	Germany - Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Jülich	Sebastian Beier	0000-0002-2177-8781
FR - France	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE (INRA)	Cyril Pommier	0000-0002-9040-8733
EMBL-EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory, European Bioinformatics Institute, Wellcome Genome Campus, Hinxton, Cambridge CB10 1SD, United Kingdom	Timothee Cezard	0000-0002-5626-270X

Abbreviations and Acronyms

DROPS	D Rought- t Olerant yielding P lant S
AGENT	Activated G enebank N e T work
ISA	Investigation Study Assay Framework
RO-Crate	R esearch O bject C rate
BLUEs	B est L inear U nbiased E stimates
ARC	A nnotated R esearch C ontext
EVA	E uropean V ariation A rchive

Contents

Executive Summary	1
Document info	1
Author List	2
Abbreviations and Acronyms	2
Contents	2
Planned Approach for Generating Exemplary RO-Crates (Activity 1)	3
Adjusted Approach and Selection of an Exemplary Dataset	3
Outcomes and expected impact	3
Dissemination Plans	4
References	4

Planned Approach for Generating Exemplary RO-Crates (Activity 1)

Initially, Activity 1 was designed to focus on the FAIRification of existing plant science datasets by converting them into the machine-actionable RO-Crate format. The primary datasets selected for this process were **DROPS** and **AGENT**, with plans to extend these efforts to data from other important crops, the **PHIS** database, and studies in the **EVA** repository.

The main objectives were:

1. To **quantify the work** required to transform existing datasets into FAIR RO-Crates.
2. To **provide reference examples** that demonstrate the FAIRification process for both data producers and repositories.

To achieve this, the activity was structured around four key tasks: assessing the structure and standardization of the selected datasets (T1.1), developing a detailed conversion plan for RO-Crate compliance (T1.2), performing the conversion to identify best practices and challenges (T1.3), and adopting RO-Crate packaging in the EVA repository as a practical use case (T1.4). The intended outcome was a clear understanding of the effort involved in this process, which would inform subsequent work packages on developing guidelines and promoting FAIR practices.

Adjusted Approach and Selection of an Exemplary Dataset

In practice, the initial plan required adjustment due to external factors. Work on the **DROPS** dataset was postponed because the hiring process for the necessary personnel was delayed and is expected to resume in September. The FAIRification of the **AGENT** was finished, but as the dataset is awaiting its primary scientific publication it is currently not publicly accessible. We expect a successful publication soon and will then immediately also release the datasets. To ensure continued progress and meet the objectives of Activity 1, we pivoted to focus on a different, readily available dataset ([Philipp et al. 2019](#)). We selected a dataset from a recent publication by ([Philipp et al. 2019](#)), which provides historical phenotypic observations of 12,754 wheat accessions from the IPK Genebank, gathered over 70 years.

This dataset was an ideal alternative as it is comprehensive, well-documented, and already structured in the ISA-Tab format. It includes key agronomic traits (flowering time, plant height, thousand grain weight), extensive metadata, processed data (BLUEs), and the R scripts used for analysis. Its self-contained nature makes it a perfect candidate for creating a reference RO-Crate, allowing us to proceed with tasks T1.1, T1.2, and T1.3 and generate an exemplary dataset as planned. Using the ARCitect tool facilitated the restructuring of the dataset. The created ARC (https://git.nfdi4plants.org/arendd/Historical_Phenomics_Wheat_Collection_IPK) is publicly available in the PLANTdataHUB ([https://git.nfdi4plants.org, Weil et al. 2023](https://git.nfdi4plants.org>Weil et al. 2023)). As it is based on the [ARC-RO-Crate profile](#) it can be exported as valid RO-Crate (https://git.nfdi4plants.org/arendd/Historical_Phenomics_Wheat_Collection_IPK/-/packages) using the embedded package registry of the used GitLab infrastructure.

As part of this work package the European Variation Archive implemented a new endpoint to describe all its studies as RO-Crates. It follows the new RO-Crate version 1.2 which allows the JSON-LD document to be generated as response to a REST query rather than being a static json file. This implementation leverages a pre-existing RO-Crate profile based on the Investigation/Study/Assay (ISA) metadata standard, ensuring interoperability with other life science data infrastructures.

Outcomes and expected impact

The deliverable aligns with the major objective of applying best practices to improve data interoperability and reusability. The FAIRified datasets are based on established relevant standards such as MIAPPE, ISA and RO-Crate and help to streamline data annotation processes as well as act as reference datasets. Furthermore, the ARC-RO-Crate profile and the ARCitect tool enable the transformation of ISATAB and ISAJSON datasets into FAIR Digital Objects (RO-Crates). Accordingly, we will now commence work on updating the relevant guidelines to reflect this new capability.

Dissemination Plans

The historical wheat dataset is now publicly available in the PLANTdataHUB. As part of the HARVEST project, it will also be linked across other relevant resources and platforms (RDMkit, etc). Additionally, datasets from the AGENT and DROPS projects will be released soon, and each will be assigned a persistent DOI to ensure long-term availability.

References

Philipp N, Weise S, Oppermann M, Börner A, Keilwagen J, Kilian B, et al. Historical phenotypic data from seven decades of seed regeneration in a wheat ex situ collection. *Sci Data* 2019;6.

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Weil HL, Schneider K, Tschöpe M, Bauer J, Maus O, Frey K, et al. PLANTdataHUB: a collaborative platform for continuous FAIR data sharing in plant research. *The Plant Journal* 2023;116:974–88.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.16474>

ARC-RO-Crate profile: <https://github.com/nfdi4plants/arc-ro-crate-profile>

ARC “Historical Phenomics Wheat Collection IPK”:

https://git.nfdi4plants.org/arendd/Historical_Phenomics_Wheat_Collection_IPK